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Exploring the Impact of Technology Usurp on Job Performance among the Staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina

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ABSTRACT

The study explores the impact of Technology usurp among the staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina, Nigeria. Four research questions guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted focusing on the staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina, Nigeria on the impact of technology usurp/adaption on their job performance. The population of the study comprised all the senior non-academic staff and all academic staff of the Polytechnic. All the population formed the sample of the research so as to have greater reliability on the findings. A self-structured four points Likert type questionnaire was used as an instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was validated by experts and its reliability was determined by pilot testing and a statistical tool of Spearman-Brown Prophecy Formula. The descriptive statistic of frequency counts and percentage was used to analyze the demographic data while the mean and standard deviation was used to analyze the research questions. The results of the study indicated that technology usurps/adaption greatly improves the daily routine activities of the senior staff in the Polytechnic. It also enhances job performance of the senior staff in the Polytechnic. It was recommended among others, that all staff in the Polytechnic should be re-sensitized on the need to change their habit from analogue to digital orientation. All stakeholders in the Polytechnic should be embraced on the process of the change that is technology adaptation.

Keywords: Technology; Technology Usurp/Adaptation; Performance; Senior Staff

INTRODUCTION

The new era of globalization around the world gives birth to unprecedented innovations to meet up with the new trends of unfolding events. Among the models that are being employed today is technology usurp/adaption. Technology usurp entails the improvement of democratic processes by transforming the way public services are delivered through innovations and applications of technology to enhance planning and decision making in the organization.

Recently, technology forms a nexus for national development which an organization and its employees must embrace or else be embarrassed. It is a well-known fact that organizations today invest in technology to create and reach new markets and channels to share and distribute knowledge and information (Kharuddin & Othman, 2010). Taking this into cognizance, employees must adapt to

technological break-through so as not to extinct. Today, Higher Institutions of learning are facing serious challenges/competitions due to their proliferations in the state and the nation in general, therefore it become imperative for each institution to strive hard to exist or exit, hence innovations and adaptation is necessary. As posited by Olusanya and Oluwasanya (2014), for organizations to survive, they must its employees must adapt to the use of computer systems, database management systems and the development of effective network systems to create, store, preserve and utilize information for effective decision making; hence its employees must be conversant and must effectively be able to manipulate and use electronic devices such as laptops, palmtops, personal computers, I-pads, I-phones and any latest innovation in technology

The government, presently, as a measure of saving cost and enhancing speedy implementation of programs, recognizes technology as a strategic avenue for national development. Taking into cognizance the immense benefits therein, organizations injected considerable resources into it, and hence the resources must be put into use by its employees, hence, imperative for each employee to adapt to the tune of the piper. Technology usurps serves as a means of assessing, planning and managing development of organizations. More so, knowledge is acquired through technology and therefore adapting to it by any organization is a necessity rather than a choice.

The adaption to technology must be timely for it has an immeasurable importance and power, and is a well-known fact that power is an aphrodisiac. As posited by Hassan and Altamimi (2017), tertiary institutions thrive on new scientific discoveries and innovations through teaching and learning and effective and learned workforce who embrace technology. Teaching and learning are delivered using Information and Communication Technology (ICT) infrastructure platforms; the availability and usage of personal computers and their accessories enhances the output of staff in the institutions; visual library aids teaching and learning as well as research. These variables make an institution great and attract high ranking. But, Hassan and Altamimi (2017) maintained that these could not be achievable unless the staff can easily adapt to changing technologies.

Statement of the Problem

Polytechnics as technology-based institutions thrive to produce students/graduates who can apply scientific and technological thinking in solving problems. Its employees, both academic and non-academic staff are expected to be technology literate in all their day-to-day activities so as to make teaching and learning smoothly and the environment for the learning friendly. It was in line with this that the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) plan to digitalized all its activities in order to align with the 4th Industrial Revolution (4IR) so as to reduce the number of manpower that it mobilized for physical visitation on accreditations of all Polytechnic programs (HUK/DAP/, 2023). To achieve this, all Polytechnic staff must be involved in the transformation process, which is ICT driven process. The NBTE assumes that Polytechnic staffs are technologically transformed.

Despite the potentials for technology to transform the working behavior of staff in Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, it seems that the extent to which the staff in the Polytechnic (Academic and Non-Academics) embraced ad integrated technology into their daily routine activities is still unknown. There is also limited insights regarding the attitudes and perceptions of the staff of the Polytechnic towards technology usurp. It is also unclear to understand the factors that technology enhances productivity and efficiency, but its actual impact on the work of staff of the Polytechnic has not been evaluated.

Based on all these unanswered questions and missing links, coupled with lack of empirical evidence on whether adapting to technology leads to a better job performance and increased productivity and efficiency among staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina, Nigeria justifies this research so as to explore it.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study generally is to explore the impact of technology usurp on the job performance among the staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina, Nigeria.

Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Explore the impact of technology usurp on the productivity of staff of the Polytechnic.

2. Explore the extent to which technology usurp enhances job performance among the staff of the Polytechnic.
3. Explore the challenges faced by the staff of the Polytechnic on technology adaption.
4. Explore the ways of improving technology usurp/adaption among the staff of the Polytechnic.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How does technology usurp among the staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina improves the staff productivity in their daily routine activities?
2. To what extent does technology usurp enhances the job performance of the staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina?
3. What are the challenges of technology usurp by the staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic in adapting to technology?
4. What are the measures/ways to be used to ease technology adaption among the staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina?

Review of Related Literature

Technology

The dynamic nature of technology has contributed to the existence of various definitions. It is an inherently abstract concept that is difficult to interpret, observe and evaluate. Its definition varies according to authors and the context of disciplines. Kumar (1999) maintained that technology consists of two components, namely: a physical component that comprises items such as products, tools, equipment, blue-prints, techniques and processes. The second component is informational component. This component consist the know-how in management, quality control and reliable workforce. Based on the stands of Kumar, two basic components must be available before technology emerges, that is, knowledge/techniques and doing things the right way. Technology is always connected with obtaining results, solving certain problems, completing tasks using particular skills, employing knowledge and exploiting assets.

Psicco-Smart Editorial Team (2024) posits that technology is a cultural system concerned with the relationships between humans and their environment. To Hendricks (2000) technology encompasses the basic knowledge of sub-system, the technical support system (software) and the capital-embodied technology (hardware). Perceived differently, Barbour (1993) defines technology as the application of organized knowledge to practical task by ordered systems of people and machines. Friedel (2007) maintains that technology is the knowledge and instruments that humans use to accomplish the purpose of life. In the economist perspectives, technology is the ability to convert society's resources (labour and capital) into output (goods and services that the society value. Moreover, Ramanathan (2024) views technology as the application of scientific knowledge to the practical aims of human life or, it is sometimes phrased, to the change and manipulation of human environment. But, Thierer (2024) says, technology is the understanding of craftsmanship – not simply the way (or ways) in which a thing is done, but the study of the ways things are done.

Technology according to Oregon State University (2024) can be perceived in four different perspectives. Firstly, it is the rational process of creating means to order and transform matter, energy and information to realize certain values. Secondly, it is the set of means (tools, devices, systems, procedures) created by the technological process. Thirdly, it is the knowledge that makes technological process possible. It consists of the facts and procedures necessary to order and manipulate matter, energy and information, as well as how to discover new means to such information. Fourthly, it is a sub-set of related technological objects and knowledge, and fifthly, it is the system consisting of the technological process, objects, knowledge; develops of technological objects and the worldwide (i.e., the beliefs about things and the value of things that shape how one views the world) that has emerged from and drives the technological process. While the University adopted the fifth perspectives of the technology, the researcher adopted the third and the fifth respectively.

Based on all the definitions, technology must have the attributes of implementation, which states that it should not be based on “empty-headedness”; it should be practicable, that is not “for its own sake”; it should be embodied, that is “not in the head alone” and it must be intelligent, that is “not blind”.

Technology Adaptation/Usurp

Adapting to new technology in the workplace can improve teams’ efficiency and contribute effectively to the achievement of the organizational strategic planning. Employees must be motivated and encourage embracing any new technology so as to move the organization to the next level of development. Technology is an essential component in every work environment. Ashley (2024) outlines the reasons for technology adaption as follows:

- 1) **It can boast the efficiency of the organization:** Many technologies actually make the jobs easier and quicker which metamorphoses to boasting the organization image and goodwill.
- 2) **Engagement in team work:** Adapting to technology provides team work in any environment. New tools connect and engage all team together, each employee performing his segmented part, which at the end of the day, the fragments becomes a whole.
- 3) **It improves teams’ productivity:** When team members know how to use technology, they can improve their productivity and achieve shared goals more quickly.
- 4) **It empowers employee’s growth:** When each employee/team is given the right tool adapting the new technology in the workplace empowers their professional growth and development. New skills can be learned to broaden their knowledge, thus, minimizing skills gaps within the organization.
- 5) **It encourages competition:** Technology is a key part of staying competitive in today’s changing world. An organization must streamline its operations and develop innovative solutions to meet the competition.

Employees Resistance to Adapt to New Technology

Employees’ resistance to change or adapt to a change in terms of using a new systems, a new process or a new technology metamorphoses to inability to achieve organizational objectives of the organization. The resistance could be internal which could result to loss of productivity, employees getting frustrated who eventually may lead to quitting the job or being fired as a result of low productivity or outright hostility. Others may include employee tenure, scale of change and team involvement.

Resistance to change could be of three types as outlined by Jones and Ven (2016) as follows:

- a) **Logical Resistance:** This kind of resistance basically arises from the time employees genuinely take to adapt and adjust to changes. For example, when computers became common, accountants had to shift from accounting on paper to digital accounting. This naturally takes time to adapt. In educational institutions, the work pattern was in most cases done in an analogue way, adapting to the digital system has to take time. Therefore, if extra caution is not exercise on how the change pattern should be done, employees normally resist to it. Also, the older generation in any organization (who in most cases are analogue) cannot easily be transformed to the digital system. Organizations should plan the transition to be logical and with less tension.
- b) **Psychological Resistance:** This occurs to purely due to mental and psychological factors like fears of the unknown, less tolerance in change and dislike towards the organizational management. Employees feel that technology may displace them in a long run. Their schedules will be assimilated by the technology and therefore, may resist to the change. Some may not accept the change due to the fact that their expertise in the analogue way of doing things will be overtaken by the digital system. More so, the gains derivable from the analogue way of doing things will be exposed by the technology and hence the adaption will not be welcomed by them. Some employees may put the blame to the management that the technology is only a system of witch-hunting them and exposing their loopholes. Those employees having this type of perception resist violently to any new technology.
- c) **Sociological Resistance:** This resistance relates not to individuals in the organization but rather to the common values and customs of groups. Some individuals may be willing to change but will not due to peer pressure from the group they are members. The sociological resistance stems from organized labor unions or pressure groups in the organization. Until and unless the labor union and pressure groups are brought on board and taken care off, employees may resist to adapt to any new technology.

Reasons for Employees Resistance to Adapt to a New Technology

Employees generally find it convenient to continue doing things as they have always been doing it. Learning something new usually becomes difficult for them. It is pertinent to know that change always bring about alterations in a person's duties, powers and influence. Hence, employees to whom such changes will affect negatively will resist. It is also a well-known fact that employees who are adamant on maintaining customs instead of taking risks and doing new things will always resist to adapt.

Apart from the types of resistance mentioned earlier, employees resist to adapt to new technology due to so many reasons as outlined below:

1) **Mistrust and Lack of Confidence:** Employees may resort to resist any technology once they have no trust to their management and lack confidence on any information that the management may render to them as the reasons for the technology. The mistrust could be due to past experiences employees had on the organizational policies or it could be due to the persons shouldered with the responsibility of championing the process. If the employees have no confidence in him due to his human nature or due to lack of human relations and many other factors the adaption process will almost be impossible (Kanter, 1985).

2) **Emotional Responses:** Employees in most cases become emotionally unstable as a result of any new innovation. The time it will take them to learn it, the conditions attached to the technology, the environment itself, the working conditions and the overall welfare of the employees. Change take place only and when the employees are financially buoyant and can naturally take care of themselves and their family financially. So, once a technology is introduced and the employees are unstable in their basic needs, they will emotionally resist it (Leigh, 2002; Steptoe, Fieldman Evans & Perry, 1993).

3) **Lack of Training and Help Resources:** Technology adaption could be greatly hindered as a result of lack of training. Any new thing introduced must be accompanied with training and the training must be systematic and rigorous. In as much as training is not adequately conducted on any new technology, there may be a greater probability that the employees will resist to it because they cannot render what they don't have. The resistance could be obstacle with lack or inadequate resources. The employees must be provided with adequate and functional technology to be trained on if they adaption process is intended to be achieved. A part from the resources, the resource persons that will facilitate the training should be versatile and expert in the field of the technology and education. They must have knowledge of teaching and how to impart the needed knowledge and therefore, apart from being expert in their field they must have sound knowledge in education and educational psychology (Mckay, Kuntz & Nawzal, 2013)..

4) **Poor Change Communication:** This is another important impediment to adapting to a new technology by employees. Change communication is the system of sensitizing all and sundry on the reasons that every employee must embrace a new technology. The employees must be adequately sensitized on the advantages of the technology and its needs to the organization. The employees must be given adequate lectures with a vivid comparison of the organization and similar organizations'. The employees should be sensitized on the consequences awaiting everybody in the organization as a result of the failure to adapt to a technology. They should be sensitized on the competitive nature of the society and that competition can only be taken care if all and sundry adapt. The employees must be aware that their inability to adapt could lead to their job insecurity (Swanson & Holton, 2001).

5) **Fear of Failure:** Employees adamant to adapt sometimes is attributed to their fear of failure. No body want to be found wanting in his assigned task. The summations of the fragment parts make a whole. In this situation, an employee may have fear that if he cannot play his part as expected and the failure results from his part, he will be held responsible for that. If many employees have this fear, definitely adaption to any technology will be quite impossible or will take a long time to actualize.

6) **Unrealistic Time Lines:** Once a scheduled have been drawn on the transition from old way of doing things in an analogue way to the new way of doing things in a digital way, and the result do not poster a reality of the environment or organization, employees resist to it. In a situation where the employees are always busy with their daily routine tasks and training or something else intrude, they may likely be confused and in the long run be 'Jack of all and master of none' (Jones & Vein, 2016).

- 7) **Existing Organization Culture and Norms:** This is another factor that negates adaption. The existing organization culture and the norms may have an adverse effect on adaption process. If the organization have a well discipline procedures and zero tolerance to failure, its employees will easily adapt to any new technology. Once the norms of the organization are a laissez faire to rules, discipline and employees misbehavior, adapting to a new technology will almost be impossible. Lack of employee support to change is sometimes as a result of lack of work integrity. The employees seem care only on their take home not the service they will render to the organization (Leigh, 2002).
- 8) High cynicism and Organizational Silence, uncomfortable work environment and absolute silence on the organizations problems and progress attributed to resistance to adaption (Reiches, Wanous & Austin, 1977; Morrison & Milliken, 2000).
- 9) Decrease in Organizational Support and Organizational Justice also contributed to resistance to change by employees (Jones & Vein, 2016).

METHOD

This chapter describes the method used in conducting the research. It discusses the research design, area of the study, population of the study, sample, sampling techniques, instrument for data collection, validation of the instrument, reliability of the instrument, method of data collection and method of data analysis.

This study adopted descriptive research design due to the fact that opinion of employees were sought on the impact of technology usurp/adaption on job performance in Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina, Nigeria. The design also describes and interprets “what is” of the research. It also seeks to find out the conditions or relationships that exists, opinions that are held, processes that are going on, effects that are evident or trends that are developing in the topic (Nworgu, 2010). This design correlates with the views of Cohen, Mannion and Morrison (2010) that posit descriptive research design as the type of research that gather data at a particular point in time with the intention of describing or identifying standards against which existing conditions can be compared, or determining the relationships that exist between events. More so, Iro (2017) adopted this type of research design in his research titled “Employers assessment of adequacy of Office Technology and Management Curriculum for graduates’ employability skills acquisition in North-West Nigeria and was successful.

The area of the study is Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina, Nigeria. The institution was established on the 1st January, 1983 as Katsina Polytechnic and subsequently amended by Law of 2003 as Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic. The objectives for the establishment of the institution is to provide courses of study, training and research in sciences, technology, social sciences and the humanities as well as any other sphere of learning approved by the Academic Board for the purpose of entry requirements into universities and other institutions of higher learning; to offer courses of study at Post-graduate Diploma, Higher National Diploma, National Diploma and Certificate Courses in sciences, technology, social sciences and the humanities as well as any other sphere of learning approved by the Academic Board; to provide courses of in-service instruction for members of the public service of the state and to the extent that the Academic Board deems fit, courses of the like nature for persons unconnected with any of the public services of the state; to promote through teaching, research and technological advancement of knowledge and its practical application to the needs of the community and to provide entrepreneurial skills to students that will assist to benefit the state and Nigeria at large.

The institution is situated along Tafawa Balewa Road, Katsina between 4.4 and km 11.2 along western side trunk ‘B’ road linking Katsina city with Dutsin-ma. The Polytechnic is bordered by Federal College of Education at the Eastern part; Jangebe village at the western part, Al-Qalam University at Southern part and General Amadi Rimi Orthopedic Hospital the Northern Part.

The population of the study comprised all the senior non-academic staff and all senior academic staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina. The total population of the study is 659 staff of the Polytechnic, comprising of 245 senior non-academic staff and 414 academic lecturers. The researcher used all the population as sample for the study because the number is manageable, to enhance greater reliability.

The researchers used a structured four points Likert-Type Questionnaire having variables and weight as follows: Strongly Agree (SA=4), Agree (AG=3), Disagree (DG=2) and Strongly Disagree (SD=1). The questionnaire consisted of two sections namely: Section A and B. Section A delved on the biographic data of the respondents which include the gender, status and salary grade level. Section B which was further divided into four clusters, each cluster dealt with a single research question and its item statements. The instruments were validated by panel of experts and their reliability coefficients were determined.

The structured questionnaire was validated by two experts as follows: A Chief Lecturer from the Department of Business Administration and Management, Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina and the ICT Director of the Polytechnic. The validators were given title of the study, purpose of the study, research questions alongside the instrument. They were requested to face validate the instrument on its possibility to elicit the needed information, its scope, language clarity and overall adequacy of the items as well as make modifications as they deem fit.

The research instrument was subjected to reliability test so as to determine its internal consistency. Split half method was used where 40 copies of the instrument were distributed to the similar population at Federal Polytechnic Daura. Data were analyzed with Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and reliability coefficients of 0.89, 0.75, 0.78 and 0.92 were obtained for the clusters. K-R statistical formula was used to obtain the overall reliability coefficient and 0.81 was obtained. Based on this, the instrument was adjudged to be reliable as posited by Nworgu (2010), that any instrument with r value from 0.75 and above is considered to be reliable.

The Lead Researcher, two research partners and three research assistants distributed the questionnaire to the respondents. The research assistants were trained on the techniques of the distribution and collection of the questionnaire. At first instance, the number of questionnaire was distributed. The respondents were given two weeks to complete the questionnaire. At the expiration of the time given, the Lead Researcher, Research Partners and the Research Assistants retrieved the filled questionnaires from the respondents.

The retrieved numbers of the questionnaire were analysed using descriptive statistics. Section A was analyzed using percentage method. Any item with the percentage above 50 percent was considered. Section B was analyzed with mean and standard deviation. Any item with a mean score equals to or above 2.5 was accepted and vice-versa. The standard deviation was used to ascertain the homogeneity of the responses.

RESULTS

Research Question One: 1. *How does technology usurp among the staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina improves the staff productivity in their daily routine activities?*

Analysis of research question one is presented in Table II

Table II: Improvement of Productivity as result of Technology Adaption				N=612
S/No	Items Statement	Mean	Stand. Dev.	Remark
1	It increases team and individual performance	2.70	0.91	SA
2	It increases individual performance	2.80	0.98	SA
3	It boast efficiency of the organization	2.68	1.00	SA
4	Team work is highly encouraged	2.59	1.04	SA
5	Employees working habit changed	2.83	0.95	SA
6	Completion of work within shortest time	2.81	0.86	SA
7	Staff becomes innovative	2.50	1.01	SA
8	Staff changed to digital orientation	2.49	1.06	SD
9	Staff feels proud for the progress of the org.	2.52	1.01	SA
Grand Mean/Standard Deviation		2.65	0.75	SA

Source: Questionnaire, 2025

Data in Table II reveals that senior staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic Katsina agreed that adapting technology greatly improves their productivity in their daily routine activities with the exception

of item serial No. 8 that is staff changed to digital orientation, which has a mean rating of 2.49. This was attested glaringly based on the fact that all the item statements have a mean above 2.50. More so, the grand mean of 2.65 further supported their responses. The standard deviation and the grand standard deviation indicate the homogeneity of their responses.

Research Question Two: *How does technology usurp enhances job performance of the senior staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic Katsina?*

Responses to research question two is presented in Table three

Table III: Technology Usurp enhancing job performance in Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic N=612

S/No	Item Statement	Mean	Stand. Dev	Remarks
1	Work flows continuously and naturally	2.50	0.98	SA
2	There is a seamless work pattern	2.85	0.89	SA
3	Time management was respected	2.78	0.92	SA
4	Accuracy in work is increased	2.73	0.81	SA
5	Job collaborations is encouraged	2.58	0.83	SA
6	There have been accessibility and flexibility	2.71	0.78	SA
7	Service is enhanced	2.56	0.82	SA
8	Improve communication and collaboration	2.49	0.79	SD
9	Enhance data management and access	2.48	0.80	SD
10	Staff embraced technology	2.49	0.78	SD
Grand Mean/Standard Deviation		2.70	0.84	SA

Source: Questionnaire, 2025

Table III shows that technology enhances job performance among senior staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic. The Table revealed that 08 out of the ten item statement were experienced as a result of technology adaption. The staffs were of the opinion that improved communication and collaboration; enhancing data management and access and staff embracing technology have some lapses. The items reveal mean ratings of 2.49, 2.48 and 2.49 respectively below the cut-off mean of 2.50. Nevertheless, the grand mean of 2.70 indicated that technology adaption enhances job performance among the senior staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic. The grand standard deviation of 0.84 shows the homogeneity of the responses.

Research Question Three: *What are the challenges to technology usurp/adaptation by the senior staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina?*

Responses to research question three is presented in Table Four

Table Four: Challenges faced by senior staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic on technology usurp N=612

S/No	Item Statement	Mean	Stand. Dev.	Remarks
1	Mistrust and lack of confidence	2.67	0.97	SA
2	Emotional responses	2.82	0.83	SA
3	Inadequate training	2.63	0.79	SA
4	Inadequate resource persons/help resource	2.52	0.81	SA
5	Fear of failure	2.70	0.82	SA
6	Unrealistic time lines for adaption	2.88	0.90	SA
7	Organization's norms and culture	2.58	0.85	SA
8	Inadequate communication	2.51	0.86	SA
9	Shortage of equipment/tools	2.55	0.79	SA
10	Fear of the unknown	2.90	0.87	SA
11	Electricity/power failure	2.93	0.95	SA
Grand Mean/Standard Deviation		2.69	0.85	SA

Source: Questionnaire, 2025

Data presented in Table Four indicated that all the respondents agreed to all the item statement as challenges to technology usurp in Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic Katsina. All the items have mean ratings between 2.51 to 2.90. This was in consonance to the decision rule that any item with mean ratings 2.50 and above is considered as agreed. But, with a cursory looking at the Table, the senior staff of the Polytechnic weighted emotional responses; unrealistic time lines for adaption; fear of the unknown and electricity/power failure as challenges to technology usurp to them. The items have mean ratings of 2.82; 2.88; 2.90 and 2.93 respectively. The standard deviation revealed the homogeneity of the responses.

Research Question Four: *What are the measure/ways to be used to ease technology adaption by the senior staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina?*

Responses to question four is presented in Table Five

Table V: Ways to ease technology adaptation by the senior staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic N = 612

S/No	Item Statement	Mean	Stand. Dev.	Remarks
1	Provision of adequate resource	3.05	1.06	SA
2	Provision of adequate resource persons	3.01	1.00	SA
3	Incorporating employees/labour leaders in the management pattern	2.98	0.97	SA
4	Effective and clear communication	2.78	0.98	SA
5	Understanding the importance of technology	2.99	1.01	SA
6	Mutual understanding in the work place	2.82	0.88	SA
7	Understanding the technology	3.00	0.99	SA
8	Adequate training	3.03	1.02	SA
9	Reward system for success	3.01	0.99	SA
10	Respecting the opinion of the employees	2.92	0.89	SA
11	Provision of solar power system	3.03	0.95	SA
Grand Mean/Standard Deviation		2.96	0.97	SA

Data in Table Five revealed that senior staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic Katsina strongly agrees that if all the item statement listed in this Table are applied, technology adaption by all of them will be a reality and it will be done within shortest period of time. All the item statements have mean rating ranging from 2.82 to 3.05. The grand mean of 2.96 further attested to the responses. The standard deviation reveals the homogeneity of the responses.

Summary of Findings

The following were findings of the study as deduced from the results of the analyzed questionnaire.

1. Adaptation to technology greatly improves the daily routine activities of the staff in the Polytechnic.
2. Usurp to technology enhances job performance of the Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic senior staff.
3. Even though the job performance have been enhanced, senior staff of the Polytechnic were bedeviled with serious challenges, among which are mistrust and lack of confidence, emotional responses, inadequate training, inadequate resource person/help resources, fear of failure, unrealistic time lines for the adaption, organization norms and culture, uncomfortable working environment, inadequate communication, shortage of equipment/tools, power failure and fear of the unknown.
4. The staff has expressed hope that if the following measures will be taken, adapting to any technology will be simple. The measures are: understanding the technology and its importance, identifying technical experts in the immediate domain of the staff, training, reward system for

the initial stage of the adapting process, effective and clear communication and provision of solar system to all offices.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Improvement of senior staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina productivity on their daily routine activities as a result of technology usurp/adaptation

The result of the analyses presented showed that senior staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic Katsina productivity greatly increased as a result of adapting to technology. The senior staff of the Polytechnic maintained that as a result of adapting to technology, their team and individual performances increased. The increase in the individual and team performances resulted in the efficiency of the organization. They attested that their working habit changed as such it resulted to completion of any assigned duty within shortest possible time. The staff becomes innovative which make them to be proud for self-esteem. This finding is consonance with the findings of Bala (2022) in a study conducted in North Central Nigeria that change greatly enhances growth and development of any organization. Similarly, the findings reveal that senior staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic Katsina was slow to change form analogue way to digital way of doing things. This attest the findings of Nourhussen (2024) in a study conducted at Sweden that rigid culture of the employees to change has a negative impact to the progress of the organization.

Technology Adaptation/Usurp Enhancing Job Performance in Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic

The results of the research question above reveals that technology adaption by senior staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic Katsina greatly enhances job performance of the institution. The staff maintained that work flows naturally and seamlessly without much glitch, there have been increased in accuracy of the work due to effective time management; flexibility in doing job became the order of the day due to collaboration which enhances effective work delivery. This finding attest the Organizational Adaptation Theory as stated by Hendricks that businesses will change how they operate or function in an effort to keep up with changing market conditions or shifting environment factors. But the findings reveals that the senior staff of the Polytechnic improved communication and collaboration, data management and access and full embracing the technology is not fully accomplished. This negative attitude attests the findings of Mannes (2020) in a research conducted in university of Stavanger that communication can influence discrepancy in job performance as a result of it being ineffective or barred by some factors, hence change to be effective, it must be appropriately tackled.

Challenges encountered by senior staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic associated with technology usurp/adaptation

The results of the analyses on the challenges encountered by senior staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina associated with technology adaption reveals that the staff have mistrust and lack of confidence with the technology; they have emotional response and feeling that some of their activities will be gulfed by the technology and therefore the possibility of losing their jobs; there have been inadequate training, because changing somebody from what he used to do to what is expected him to do will need a lot of training; the time allotted for the staff to adapt is unrealistic due to inadequate resource persons and sometimes inadequate immediate help resources who will guide the staff in case of any difficulty or glitch; shortage of equipment and tools for proper adaption, power failure and others like fear of the unknown, organizations culture and norms and uncomfortable working environment. This finding agrees with the findings of Friedel (2007) as the reasons for employees' resistance to change.

Measures to ease technology adaptation among the senior staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic.

The findings on the measures to put in place to overcome the challenges to adapting to technology by senior staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina as revealed by the findings of the research include: incorporating the employees in the change management plan; exploring and respecting the opinion of the employees in any new policy of the organization; understanding the technology and its importance to the progress of any organization; identifying technical experts and resource help at the

immediate domain of the staff; constant training; effective and clear communication coupled with adequate resources at the disposal of the staff. This tally with the findings of Mannes (2020) on change readiness: trust in change agents and its influence on five change benefits and the findings of Damawan (2020) on the strategies for effective changes. It also agrees with the findings of Bala (2022) that for an organization to explore change management, there should be coaching and orientation, personnel training, retraining and reward system.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The researchers recommended that:

1. All staff of the Polytechnic should be fully re-sensitized on the need to change their old habit (analogue) way of doing things to a modern ways (digital) of doing things.
2. The Polytechnic should embrace all stakeholders (labor unions) in the process of adapting to the new technology.
3. There should be adequate training, training facilities, help resources and the equipment to all deserving staff.
4. There should be a reward system for the staff that totally embraced the adaption process and are successful towards it.
5. The fears of the staff that the technology will replace them should be as much as possible erased.
6. The transition to technology adaption should be gradual and systematic.
7. Some colleges/departments/unit should be selected as pilot for the adaption process.

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